

NOT STICKING TO TRADITION –
DESIGNING WITH ADVANCED MATERIALS
AND ADHESIVES

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demands placed upon the design engineer to reduce operating costs and increase efficiency have led to the exploitation of new materials and the use of alternative joining techniques to those traditionally specified; adhesive technology offers a versatile and effective alternative. An example of how new materials can be combined with traditional materials to produce an exciting new opportunity will be described in detail: the replacement of a metal driveshaft with a composite driveshaft. The successful bonding of the steel drive flanges to the composite tube, which is crucial to the integrity of the drive system will be explained.

BACKGROUND

Within the last 40 years we have seen a change from the use of conventional materials, such as steels, to the use of advanced materials *e.g* fibre reinforced plastics. Plastics materials frequently have higher strength-to-weight ratios than aluminium and steel, but lower stiffness-to-weight ratio. To improve their mechanical properties, plastics can be reinforced using ceramic, metallic or polymeric fibres or particles. A significant improvement in properties is usually achieved, and the composite formed can be more economical than the polymer alone. Financial and weight advantages result. Having considered the materials briefly, we now have to ask ourselves what is the best way of assembling these materials.

The two main methods used for joining composites are mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding. Adhesive bonding is usually preferred because it does not introduce holes, which sever the fibres, act as stress raisers and can subsequently cause premature failure. In addition, mechanical fasteners can be heavy and any weight savings lost. Whilst adhesive bonding has advantages, there is still no recognised non-destructive method for checking the quality of the joint, therefore it is essential that the correct bonding procedure is carried out.

The following paper will describe the combination of metals and composites to produce a single-piece coupling shaft and the enabling technology to bond the drive flanges to the shafts.

CASE STUDY – Design and Application of Composite Cooling Tower Couplings

Introduction

Over the past three decades, power stations, refineries and large process industry have become increasingly dependent on cooling towers. Within this time, cooling towers have increased in size due to economics of scale. As a result the draft fans used on such towers have also increased in size.

Traditionally, these fans were mounted on right angle, speed reducing gear boxes which were driven via solid or small diameter tubular driveshafts by horizontal motors mounted outside the fan stacks. Larger fans required longer shafts, which led to the use of an intermediate driveshaft support bearing, and frequently, intermediate flexible couplings (Fig.1). This also meant that access to the support was required for maintenance and all too frequent repairs. Later, designers selected long, single-piece, hollow, large-diameter flexible coupling driveshafts (Fig.2) as an alternative. The use of large fans and longer shafts however was plagued with problems. A single shaft was found to be too heavy and therefore the span had to be broken up by supports. In addition, large bending loads were imposed on the shaft, vibrations high and thermal bowing a problem.

Why Single-piece Driveshafts?

One of the major advantages for moving towards a single-piece driveshaft was the elimination of the central supports, and therefore there is no need for extra access points to the shaft to be built for repairs or monitoring.

The solution to the problem was the use of composites. A carbon fibre tube was manufactured by filament winding, with the fibres wound at an angle of 12° to the horizontal. This gave the tube the best blend of longitudinal stiffness and torque capability.

The use of a composite driveshaft resulted in numerous advantages:

1. Reduced weight. The composite shaft was a tenth of the weight of the steel shaft.
2. Longer single spans. Driveshafts up to 8m long have been manufactured, without the need for a central support bearing.
3. Elimination of thermal bowing. To all practical purposes, zero coefficient of thermal expansion was achieved.
4. Corrosion resistance. The composite system selected was virtually impervious to the corrosive atmospheres experienced in this application.
5. Lower bending loads. Centre section approximately 1/10 of the weight of steel.
6. Higher fatigue load resistance. Combined with lighter weight and better balance, vibration level was reduced and fretting suppressed.
7. Bottom line. Minimal maintenance, fit-it and forget-it.

The end fittings were either 316 stainless steel or mild steel which was zinc phosphate coated to prevent corrosion problems. K500 Monel nuts and bolts were used to join the steel flanges to the end fittings.

The Enabling Technology

The successful joining of the metal flange to the composite driveshaft was crucial to the integrity of the drive system. The stress distribution between the components and adhesive dictates how well a joint will perform under load controlling how and when the unit will fail when overloaded. The specification required for the bond was:

1. Fatigue and environmental resistance.
2. Ease of application/automation.
3. Reproducible.

After installation, the adhesively bonded joint must be capable of sustaining the loads transmitted through the driveshaft, without it being the limiting factor.

Design for Bonding

One problem with an adhesively bonded joint, unlike a welded joint, is the difficulty of conducting meaningful non-destructive tests on the joint. While non destructive techniques can confirm the presence of adhesive, they cannot, as yet, ascertain the degree of adhesion between the surfaces. It is essential therefore that the geometry of the joint is optimised and the correct quality assurance procedures for applying the adhesive followed.

It is beneficial to design a component in such a way that the performance of the adhesively bonded joint will be complemented by the geometry of the final component rather than being reduced by it. This is achieved by designing the joint so that the forces experienced in the joint tend to compress the adhesive. If this cannot be done, the design should aim to induce compression and shear loads in the joint. Cleavage forces must be kept away from the vulnerable edge of the joint (1).

Bearing in mind the above, two joint designs were chosen for evaluation (Figs 3 & 4). The joint design in Fig.3 is of a typical joint that has been used very successfully in other applications. The joint design ensures complete sealing. The taper forces the adhesive both forward and backward ensuring the gap becomes completely filled while minimising peel loads at the end of the adhesively bonded joint.

The second joint design (Fig.4) shows an alternative approach, in which an interference fit joint is used. This approach allows ease of assembly and a thinner bondline and so aids accuracy in manufacturing the long driveshafts under consideration in this case.

The use of additional mechanical locking (i.e. rivets) was reviewed and eventually added to the design. This was because of the sub-zero temperatures the bond could be subjected to (-25°C), forcing the spigot to shrink away from the composite tube. With the rivet in place a slight compression load is applied to the joint which has a beneficial effect. Due to the acute angle of winding, the severing of some of the filaments was not considered to detract significantly from the strength of the tube (depending on the joint configuration).

PROCESS DEVELOPMENT

Adhesive Selection

The specification for the adhesive was:

Minimum shear strength – steel to composite

2000psi

Working temperature range	45°C to -25°C
Humidity	100%
Operating atmosphere	Saline/slightly acidic
Have a practical pot and shelf life.	
Be resistant to bacterial and UV degradation.	

Four types of adhesive met the requirements:

- (a) Single part epoxies
- (b) Two part epoxies
- (c) Acrylics
- (d) Anaerobics

On evaluating the adhesives, single epoxies were rejected because of the heat required for curing and they could not be used for gaps of less than 0.05mm.

For the first joint design (Fig.3), a two part epoxy was found to be most suitable because of room temperature curing. An alternative approach was to use a toughened anaerobic adhesive. Though relatively easy to use they cannot cope with gaps greater than 0.25mm. They are particularly useful for co-axial assemblies (Fig.4), where their small gap filling properties allow a thinner bondline. However, they are less robust than epoxy adhesives.

The final joint design implemented is shown in Fig.5 (a combination of the joint designs in Figs. 3 & 4). The steel flange was tapered with an initial interference fit for location of the tube. The taper allowed for an increase in bondline thickness ensuring good fatigue strength. This resulted in the use of Permabond E32 (a two part epoxy). This was due to the adhesive having a reasonable shelf and pot life, not requiring any heat for curing, reasonable cost, good fatigue strength and fracture toughness, allowed for the increase in bondline thickness, very low toxicity and generally there was more available data on epoxies than other adhesives which gave confidence to the user.

Surface Preparation

The following surface preparations were required for the two substrates:

Steel

- (a) The surface was degreased with a solvent
- (b) The surface to be bonded was grit blasted and degreased again
- (c) Sufficient time for the solvent to evaporate completely was allowed
- (d) The bonding operation was carried out

Epoxy Composite

- (a) The surface was degreased with methyl alcohol or isopropyl alcohol
- (b) The surface to be bonded was abraded and degreased again
- (c) The bonding operation was carried out

Manufacturing

The adhesive was applied by injecting into equi-spaced radial holes in the tubing until it was seen to be weeping out of both the top holes and the two adjacent holes on either side of the injection hole. The injection hole was then taped up and the process repeated until the joint

was filled. The adhesive was left to cure. Rivets were inserted through the injection holes. Extreme care was taken at every juncture to ensure the work was kept free of contamination and no voids or lack of adhesion existed between tube and flange.

ASSESSMENT

The adhesive stress distribution was modelled at TWI. By profiling the ends of the joint (producing a fillet between 45–60°), the stress concentrations were minimised. The reduction in stress concentrations gave a significant improvement on fatigue life.

Tensile shear tests were carried out to assess the bond strength between the composite shaft and metal plate. Most failures occurred by delamination of the composite. Where failure occurred in the joint area, this resulted mainly from the presence of voids in the adhesive. Despite this effect, there was no significant difference in the overall failure stress.

Table 1 shows the variation in test results. These were relatively consistent with an average failure stress of 96.3N/mm² and a standard deviation of ± 6.45 .

After some torsional trials undertaken at TWI had been successfully carried out, the first prototype driveshafts were installed, in Strasbourg, Germany and Fife, Scotland. Both are running satisfactorily.

SUMMARY

With the enabling technology of adhesives, a steel driveshaft had been replaced successfully with a composite driveshaft.

This case study clearly demonstrates the use of fibre reinforced plastics for use in the manufacture of driveshafts. The metal end fitting was retained as part of the design, and to enable this to be done, adhesives were successfully used to carry out the jointing procedure. However, care must be taken with joint geometry and in adopting quality systems for using adhesives.

This case study highlights the potential for adhesive technology to enable exciting new designs to be implemented.

THE FUTURE

Other areas in which a similar system to the one described could be implemented are:

- Driveshafts in deep well pumps
- Agitators in sewage ponds
- Stern tube driveshafts in ships

REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith (1986a) Design of adhesively bonded joints. In F L Matthews (ed) Joining Fibre-Reinforced Plastics Chpt 7, pp.271–311, Elsevier Applied Science.

Table 1 Tensile shear test results of adhesive joints

Testpiece	Description	Fracture Force	Failure Stress	Mode of Failure
TT1	Adhesive Joint	15.8	91	Delamination
TT2	Adhesive Joint	24.0	92.2	Delamination
TT3	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet	26.3	94.6	Delamination
TB1	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet	23.1	96.7	Bond (Void)
TB2	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet	23.2	91.2	Delamination
TB3	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet	19.1	96.9	Bond (Void)
B11-1	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet Both Ends	19.2	97.7	Delamination
B11-2	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet Both Ends	22.5	92.8	Delamination
B21-1	Adhesive Joint + One Rivet Both Ends	23.5	96.6	Bond (Void) + Delamination
B2-1	Adhesive Joint + Two Rivets Both Ends	51.6	106.9	Bond
B2-2	Adhesive Joint + Two Rivets Both Ends	42.8	88.7	Bond (Void)
B2-3	Adhesive Joint + Two Rivets Both Ends	53.5	110.6	Bond

Figure 1 Typical two-piece cooling tower fan drive

Figure 2 Single span driveshaft in which a composite shaft weighs 13kg compared to a metal shaft weighing 118kg

Figure 3 Possible joint design for the attachment of a steel flange to a composite tube using epoxy adhesive

Figure 4 Possible joint design for the attachment of a steel flange to a composite tube using adhesives

Figure 5 Final joint design selected for the attachment of a steel flange to a composite tube using an epoxy adhesive